

Kinetic Study of the Reaction Between Mandelic Acid and Chlorine

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The reaction between mandelic acid and chlorine has been found to be of second order. The rate has been found to be maximum at pH ~ 4.40, and is influenced by the presence of anions like sulphate, acetate and chloride. The value of energy and entropy of activation respectively are 30.4 k.cals. and 6.8 e.u. The reactive species is a combination of (HClO + Cl₂) with $k\text{HClO} \gg k\text{Cl}_2$. A suitable mechanism has been proposed.

MANDELIC acid has been estimated by oxidants like periodate¹, permanganate² and ceric sulphate³. Some work seems to have been done on the kinetics of the oxidation of mandelic acid by different oxidising agents⁴⁻⁷ but no work has been done on its kinetic studies with chlorine. The present studies have been undertaken to determine the influence of hydrogen ion concentration on the reaction rates and to suggest a suitable reaction mechanism.

Experimental

Reagents :

The chemicals employed were B.D.H. Analar products and were used without further purification. The reagents used with thiosulphate (0.0025 *N*), chlorine (0.0125 *M*) and mandelic acid (0.0125 *M*), except in cases of experiments using excess of chlorine or sodium mandelate.

Procedure :

25 ml. of 0.0125 *M* hypochlorite was kept for half an hour in the constant temperature bath and an equivalent quantity to that of hypochlorite present of 0.0125 *M* mandelic acid (which had also been kept at the same temperature of the bath for about half an hour was added and the whole made up to 100 ml. The timer was started during the mixing. At definite intervals of time, 10 ml. of the reaction mixture were pipetted out and added to an excess of potassium iodide and sulphuric acid (15 ml. of 0.2 *N* KI solution and 15 ml. of 2 *N* H₂SO₄). The iodine evolved was titrated against 0.0025 *N* thio-sulphate solution using starch as indicator. The difference between the two titre values (i.e., blank and that of reaction mixture) at definite intervals of time represented the amount of mandelic acid oxidised at a particular stage. The hypochlorite content of the solution was found out using the arsenite method⁸ and the same was used in studies on rate constants.

Reaction Rates :

The data (Table 1) indicate the results obtained with excess of chlorine or increasing concentrations of sodium mandelate at 35° ± 0.1°. The results showed that the order of reaction in each case was unity—the over all order being two. In cases of experiments, using excess of chlorine or increasing concentrations of sodium mandelate, 0.01 *N* and 0.001 *N* thiosulphate were used respectively.

In cases of studies using excess of chlorine or sodium mandelate, a plot of log (*a* - *x*) against time in minutes was a straight line from whose slope *k*₁ (first order constant) was calculated.

First order constant using excess of chlorine or sodium mandelate

TABLE 1A

Temperature = 30° ± 0.1°		Mean pH = 5.34
Mandelic acid × 10 ⁻³ <i>M</i>	Chlorine × 10 ⁻³ <i>M</i>	<i>k</i> × 10 ⁻⁵ min. ⁻¹
0.625	12.75	7.67

TABLE 1B

Sodium mandelate × 10 ⁻³	16.66	20.00	25.00
<i>k</i> ₁ × 10 ⁻³ min. ⁻¹	83.05	110.20	153.70
<i>k</i> ₁ /sodium mandelate	4.99	5.51	6.15
Mean value of <i>k</i> ₁ /sodium mandelate = 5.53 ± 0.62 mole ⁻¹ min. ⁻¹ .			

Second order constants using Equivalent Concentrations of reactants at 30° ± 0.1°

Table 2 indicates the result of the investigations of the second order constants using equivalent concentrations of reactants. On plotting the values of 1/*a* - *x* against time in minutes, a straight line was

obtained in these cases. From the slope, the value of k_2 (second order constant) was obtained.

TABLE 2

Mean pH	k lit.mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹ $\times 10^{-3}$	
4.14	86.13	
4.25	118.34	(used HClO instead of NaClO)
4.40	112.20	
4.93	59.30	
5.33	36.00	
7.18	53.30	
6.73	109.30	(in presence of 0.025M Na ₂ SO ₄)
6.90	89.30	(in presence of 0.025M CH ₃ COONa)
8.15	133.40	(used HClO instead of NaClO)
8.25	77.70	
9.08	71.60	
10.53	5.30	

Effect of temperature :

The data on studies of the effect of temperature in the temperature range (30°-35°) are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3

Temperature °C	pH	k lit.mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹ $\times 10^{-3}$
30	4.93	59.30
35	4.90	134.70

Effect of Increasing Concentration of Chloride Ions :

The result of these investigations are summarized in Table 4.

TABLE 4

No.	Chloride ion concentration	K lit.mole ⁻² sec ⁻¹ $\times 10^{-3}$
1.	Nil	112.20
2.	0.15M	638.10
3.	0.20M	852.30
4.	0.25M	1061.30

The observed values of rate constant (at 30°) were compared with the calculated values of concentration of different species present in the reaction mixture at the middle stage of the reaction (at 25°). For calculating the concentration of mandelic acid molecule and mandelate ions, the following equilibrium was employed.

Out of the above four possibilities, the data given under II and IV are in agreement with the experimental results.

The second order constants (at 30°) have been plotted against the pH of the reaction medium (in the pH range 4 to 7) alongwith the calculated values of the main reactive species, (HClO+Cl₂) \times (C₆H₅CHOHCOO⁻) at 25° at the middle stage of the reaction (Tables 2 and 5, Fig. 1). A perusal of the accompanying figure shows that the two curves are almost identical which indicates the possibility

Fig. 1. Mandelic acid vs. chlorine

— O — Calculated values of concentrations at the middle stage $[HClO + Cl_2][C_6H_5CHOHCOO^-] \times 7.5 \times 10^{-4}$
 --x-- Experimental values of rate constants $\times 10^{-3}$.

that the main reactive species may be hypochlorous acid molecule+ molecular chlorine and mandelate ion with $k_{HClO} \gg k_{Cl_2}$ in pH range 4 to 7 and (HClO+ClO⁻) \times (C₆H₅CHOHCOO⁻) in the pH range 7 to 12 due to which a second maxima is obtained in this case at pH 8.25 (Not shown in figure).

Results and Discussions

Order of Reaction :

The oxidation of mandelic acid with hypochlorite has been shown to be of second order. In this case the reaction between chlorine and reductant has been shown to be of first order with respect to each of the reactants—the total order being two.

Effect of pH :

It was found that the reaction rate of mandelic acid was maximum at pH ~ 4.40, and a second maxima was observed at pH ~ 8.25.

TABLE 5. CALCULATED CONCENTRATIONS OF COMPONENTS AT THE MIDDLE STAGE OF THE REACTION AT 25°

pH	I	II	III	IV
	$\frac{[\text{HClO}] \times [\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CHOHCOOH}]}{[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CHOHCOO}^-]}$	$\frac{[\text{HClO}] \times [\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CHOHCOO}^-]}{[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CHOHCOOH}]}$	$\frac{[\text{HClO} + \text{Cl}_2] \times [\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CHOHCOOH}]}{[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CHOHCOO}^-]}$	$\frac{[\text{HClO} + \text{Cl}_2] \times [\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CHOHCOO}^-]}{[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CHOHCOOH}]}$
1	92.23×10^{-5}	64.09×10^{-7}	15.29×10^{-4}	10.63×10^{-6}
2	14.57×10^{-4}	95.81×10^{-6}	15.52×10^{-4}	10.21×10^{-5}
3	91.18×10^{-5}	63.80×10^{-5}	91.18×10^{-5}	63.80×10^{-5}
4	17.23×10^{-5}	13.77×10^{-4}	17.23×10^{-5}	13.77×10^{-4}
5	21.29×10^{-6}	14.89×10^{-4}	21.29×10^{-5}	11.66×10^{-4}
6	17.23×10^{-8}	11.65×10^{-4}	17.51×10^{-7}	11.66×10^{-4}
7	70.99×10^{-9}	35.49×10^{-5}	70.99×10^{-9}	35.49×10^{-5}
8	44.60×10^{-10}	56.14×10^{-7}	44.60×10^{-10}	56.14×10^{-7}
9	45.81×10^{-11}	57.66×10^{-8}	45.31×10^{-11}	57.66×10^{-8}
10	40.06×10^{-12}	50.43×10^{-9}	46.01×10^{-12}	57.92×10^{-9}
11	45.81×10^{-13}	57.66×10^{-10}	45.81×10^{-13}	57.66×10^{-10}

Effect of added Electrolytes :

The results on the effect of added electrolytes show that the reactions are polar in nature and their rates are increased and influenced by the presence of anions like sulphate, acetate and chloride. Thus, the anion of this acid is the reactive species in this case against hypochlorous acid, molecular chlorine or hypochlorite anion from chlorine solution.

Thermodynamic parameters :

The higher values of energy of activation (above 20 k.cals./mole) in the case of mandelic acid ($\Delta E = 30.4$) indicate the presence of a higher order in this case. Besides, a positive value of entropy of activation ($\Delta S = 6.8$) in this case shows that here, the reaction is taking place between oppositely charged ions. Experimentally, it has been observed that no complex formation is involved in this system as confirmed by the plot of $1/k_1$ against $1/\text{sodium-mandelate}$, when a straight line passing through the origin was obtained.

The absence of free radical is indicated by the negative test with mercuric chloride.

Reactive species :

Since chlorate has been found not to react in slightly acidic, neutral or alkaline solutions (pH 4 to 10) in which range the reaction has been found to be fast, an equilibrium exists between the remaining oxidising components viz., (HClO), (ClO⁻), (Cl₂) and (Cl₃⁻).

Taking into consideration, the formation of the ions mentioned above, we have,

$$(\text{HClO}) + (\text{ClO}^-) + (\text{Cl}_2) + (\text{Cl}_3^-) = 1.5625 \times 10^{-3}$$

(at the middle stage of the reaction).

Out of the above reactive species, (ClO⁻) is maximum at high values of pH and, thus, one or more of the remaining species may be responsible for the oxidation.

Studies on the effect of added chloride were used for the calculation of K_1 (the hydrolysis constant of chlorine). On the basis of the two assumptions viz. (1) $k \text{HClO} \gg k \text{Cl}_2$ and (2) $k \text{Cl}_2 \gg k \text{HClO}$, it was found that the value of k_1 on the basis of first assumption was nearer to the theoretical value in case of mandelic acid. This assumption is further supported by the results with chlorine free unbuffered hypochlorous acid (prepared by the method using mercuric oxide and chlorine⁹ (Table 2).

Hence, we can conclude that reactive species in the case of mandelic acid may be a combination of (HClO + Cl₂) with $k \text{HClO} \gg k \text{Cl}_2$.

Reaction Mechanism :

The oxidation may be deemed to occur at the carboxylate ion via C-C fission which is indicated by the production of CO₂ (cf. oxidation of glycol or pinacol by periodate).

Thus, the oxidation of mandelic acid by hypochlorous acid or molecular chlorine can be represented by the attack of the oxidant at the carboxylate ion as shown below :

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